

INTERFACIAL ADHESION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC ACRYLIC POLYMER MATRIX CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Within several candidates of matrix polymers for carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP), acrylic polymers have high potential in terms of low-temperature processing. We focused on the improvement in the interfacial adhesive properties between CFs and the acrylic polymers using several functional monomers for the co-polymerization with methyl methacrylate (MMA). Several functional acrylic monomers were co-polymerized with the MMA, and applied as the matrix polymers of the acrylic CFRTPs. It was observed that the copolymer matrices well-adhered to the surfaces of CFs, compared to the pure PMMA. The copolymer with acrylamide (AAm) indicated higher interfacial adhesive strength than that with hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA). The hydroxyethyl acrylamide (HEAA) copolymer having both amide groups and hydroxyl groups showed very high adhesive strengths to CFs, which resulted in the high flexural strengths of the CFRTPs. The flexural strength of the pure PMMA CFRTP was 450 MPa. On the other hand, the co-polymerized acrylic matrices gave the increase in the flexural strength for the CFRTPs. Especially, the 3mol% HEAA copolymer achieved the two-fold flexural strength (900 MPa) on the acrylic CFRTP. The strength was equivalent level to the epoxy CFRP. The fatigue resistance of the HEAA copolymerized CFRTPs were also evaluated, in relation to the interfacial adhesive strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP) are light-weight materials, with high strength and elastic modulus, fracture toughness, and potential of low-cost manufacturing / secondary processing [1, 2]. Within several candidates of the thermoplastic matrices, acrylic polymers have high transparency and high potential in terms of low-temperature processing. Versatile copolymers exist in the acrylic polymers, which can be adjustable to different requirements. Here, the interfacial adhesive properties between CFs and the acrylic polymers would become key factors to realize the high potential of the acrylic CFRTPs. We focused on the improvement in the interfacial adhesive properties using several functional monomers for the co-polymerization with methyl methacrylate (MMA). Relationships between the chemical structures of the functional monomers and the mechanical properties of the CFRTPs were discussed from viewpoints of the interfacial adhesive strengths and the fracture mode of the acrylic CFRTPs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2-1 Materials

Plain woven fabrics of T300-3K carbon fibers (produced by TORAY Industries) were applied for the reinforcement materials of the acrylic CFRTPs. The basic chemical structure of the matrix polymer was poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA). Several functional monomers, such as acrylamide (AAm), 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA), N-isopropyl acrylamide (NIPAM), and hydroxyethyl

acrylamide (HEAA), were co-polymerized with the MMA. The chemical structures of the monomers are shown in Figure 1. The weight-average molecular mass of the polymers were about 350,000.

CF fabric prepreps having these several acrylic co-polymers (matrix resins) were prepared. The fiber volume content (V_f) was about 50 %.

Figure 1: Chemical structures of acrylic monomers.

2-2 Fabrication of CFRTP laminates

The fabric prepreps which consist of the CFs and the acrylic polymers were laid-up, and the CFRTP laminates were fabricated using a hot-press machine, under the pressure of 6.4MPa at 220°C.

2-3 Evaluation for mechanical properties of CFRTP laminates

Interfacial shear strengths between the CFs and the matrix polymers were evaluated in lap-shear configuration using adhered 2-layer prepreps, with a tensile strain rate of 0.5 mm / min at 25°C.

Flexural strengths of the CFRTP laminates were measured using three-point bending mode with a cross-head speed of 5 mm / min at 25°C.

Fatigue tests of the CFRTP laminates were conducted using four-point bending mode. The cyclic loading was conducted at a frequency of 5 Hz with a load ratio of 0.1 (minimum load / maximum load). Fracture surfaces were observed using an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope.

2-4 Evaluation for mechanical properties of acrylic matrix polymers

Flexural stress – strain curves of several acrylic polymers were evaluated in three-point bending mode with a cross-head speed of 5 mm / min at 25°C.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows flexural stress–strain curves of epoxy CFRP and acrylic (PMMA) CFRP. The fiber content (V_f) of these CFRPs was about 42 vol.%. The flexural strength of the epoxy CFRP was 710MPa. Whereas, the flexural strength of the PMMA CFRTP was 410MPa, corresponding to 58% of the epoxy CFRP. The initial fracture of the epoxy CFRP occurred at the tensile side of the three point bending specimens. The fracture of the

Figure 2: Flexural stress – strain curves of epoxy CFRP and acrylic (PMMA) CFRP.

PMMA CFRP occurred at the compression side of the specimens. The stress–strain curves of the PMMA CFRPs were deviated from the linear stress-strain relationship under 200MPa. Figure 3 shows the fracture surfaces. In the epoxy CFRP, the matrix resins were adhered with CFs well. On the other hand, the CFs of the PMMA CFRPs in the fractured surfaces were not covered with the matrix resins. Namely, the adhesion between CFs and PMMA was very poor. The interfacial adhesion should be an important issue to improve the mechanical properties of the acrylic CFRPs.

Epoxy CFRP **Acrylic (PMMA) CFRP**
Figure 3: Fracture surfaces of epoxy CFRP and acrylic (PMMA) CFRP.

Figure 4 shows the effect of functional monomers co-polymerized with MMA on the mechanical properties of the acrylic CFRTPs (Vf 50%). All monomers had effect on the flexural strength of the CFRTP laminates. The co-polymerization with HEAA showed the highest effect to improve the strength in all copolymers. The CFRTP having the PMMA / 3mol% HEAA copolymer matrix reached the two-fold flexural strength (900 MPa), compared to the pure PMMA matrix CFRTP (450MPa). Flexural stress–strain curves show that small amount HEAA copolymerization (1 mol%) had strong effect to the improvement in the strength of the CFRTP.

Figure 4: Effect of co-polymerization on the flexural strengths of acrylic CFRTPs.

Figure 5 shows the fractured surfaces of the acrylic CFRTPs. Copolymerization with HEA seemed to give almost no effect on the adhesion to the CFs. On the other hand, copolymerization with HEAA and AAm gave quite a few effect on the adhesion qualitatively.

Figure 5: SEM images of fractured surfaces of CFRTP specimens in the flexural tests. (a)PMMA (b) PMMA/3mol%HEA (c) PMMA/3mol%AAM (d) PMMA/3mol%HEAA

In order to quantify the increased interfacial adhesive strength between the matrix resins and the CFs, lap-shear adhesive strengths of the CFRTP laminates were evaluated. Figure 6 shows the effect of co-polymerization of functional monomers on the shear adhesive strengths of the CFRTPs. The copolymerization with HEAA and AAm gave clear effect on the shear adhesive strengths of acrylic polymers with the CFs.

Figure 6: Effect of co-polymerization on the shear adhesive strengths of acrylic CFRTPs.

Figure 7 shows the linear relationship between the shear adhesive strengths and the flexural strengths of these acrylic CFRTPs. From the data, it could be considered that the source of the high flexural strength of the acrylic CFRTP was the increased interfacial shear strength between the acrylic copolymers (HEAA, AAM) and the CFs.

Figure 7: Relationship between the shear adhesive strengths and the flexural strengths of acrylic CFRTPs.

However, it was known that the flexural strengths of the CFRPs were determined not only by the interfacial strength, but also by the elastic modulus of the matrix resins [3]. Figure 8 shows the relationship on the epoxy CFRP. The high elastic modulus of the matrix resins was an important source of the high flexural strength of the CFRP [3]. Therefore, the effect of co-polymerization on the elastic modulus of the acrylic matrix polymers was examined.

Figure 8: Relationship between the elastic moduli of epoxy matrices and the flexural strengths of the CFRPs [3].

Figure 9 shows the effect of the elastic modulus of the acrylic copolymers to the flexural strengths of the corresponding acrylic CFRTPs. The increased elastic modulus of the matrix polymers had positive effect on the flexural strengths of the acrylic CFRTPs. However, in comparison within the same elastic modulus of the matrix polymers, the flexural strengths of the CFRTPs were different among them. This shows the interfacial adhesion between the acrylic copolymers and the CFs gave major effect on the flexural strengths of the CFRTPs. The HEAA copolymerization indicated the strongest effect on the strength of the acrylic CFRTP.

Figure 9: Relationship between the elastic moduli of acrylic copolymers and the flexural strengths of the acrylic CFRTPs.

In general, copolymerization with functional monomers having amide structure gives hydrophilic property to the copolymers. Figure 10 shows the water absorption in both pure PMMA and PMMA / 3mol%HEAA copolymer at 36°C. The 3mol% HEAA copolymer absorbed more water, compared to the pure PMMA. The increase in the water absorption may deteriorate the mechanical properties of the CFRTPs. Therefore, the mechanical properties of acrylic CFRTPs were examined after 221h water absorption at 36°C, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10: Water absorption of PMMA and PMMA/3mol%HEAA.

Figure 11: Flexural stress – strain curves of PMMA / 3mol%HEAA matrix CFRTP and PMMA CFRTP - before / after water absorption -.

- PMMA / 3mol%HEAA CFRTP before water uptake
- - - PMMA / 3mol%HEAA CFRTP after water uptake
- Pure PMMA matrix CFRTP before water uptake
- - - Pure PMMA matrix CFRTP after water uptake

The flexural strengths of both PMMA CFRTP and 3mol%HEAA copolymer CFRTP decreased after the water absorption. However, the decrease ratios in the strength after the water absorption, compared to the original strength, were almost same in both CFRTPs. About 80% of the original strengths were maintained in both CFRTPs. Figure 12 shows the fracture surfaces of the water-absorbed 3mol%HEAA copolymer CFRTP. The matrix polymer (PMMA / 3mol%HEAA copolymer) had been well-adhered on the CFs even after water absorption.

Figure 12: Fracture surface of PMMA/3mol%HEAA CFRTP after water absorption.

Figure 13 shows that the 20% decrease in the strength would be due to the decrease in the elastic modulus of the matrix polymers after water absorption. As the results, the high interfacial adhesion in the CFRTP having 3mol%HEAA copolymer enabled the high mechanical strength even after water absorption.

Figure 13: Relationship between the elastic moduli of matrix resins and the flexural strengths of the CFRTPs before / after water absorption.

Cyclic loading in flexural mode was given to the acrylic CFRTPs to evaluate the fatigue resistance. Figure 14 shows the relationship between the given stress amplitude and the number of cycles to failure for the CFRTPs. The high interfacial adhesion of HEAA copolymer gave high fatigue resistance to the CFRTPs. In case of CFRTPs having 3mol%HEAA copolymer matrix, the fracture had not occurred after 7×10^6 cyclic loading under the stress amplitude of 270MPa. On the other hand, in case of CFRTPs having pure PMMA matrix, the fracture occurred after 7×10^4 cyclic loading under the stress amplitude of 90MPa.

Figure 14: Stress amplitude - Number of cycles to failure for acrylic CFRTPs (PMMA / 3mol%HEAA matrix, PMMA / 1mol%HEAA matrix, and pure PMMA matrix).

An important viewpoint was the difference of the fracture mode. Under the cyclic loading, initial micro-failure occurred at fiber / matrix interfaces in the 90° fiber bundle (weft bundle) of the fabric laminates in CFRTPs. the micro-failure grew into transverse-cracks, with increasing the number of cycles. Then, delamination which was initiated from the transverse-cracks occurred between warp and weft, or between layers. In case of pure PMMA matrix CFRTPs, the initial failure and the delamination occurred at compressive side of the flexural specimens under relatively low stress amplitude. On the other hand, the initial failure and the delamination occurred at tensile side in case of 3mol%HEAA copolymer CFRTPs having good interfacial adhesion. The high interfacial adhesion led to delay of the delamination of laminates, which also resulted in the difference in the fracture mode and the improvement in fatigue resistance.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In order to improve the interfacial adhesive properties between CFs and the acrylic polymers, several functional monomers were co-polymerized with methyl methacrylate (MMA) for fabricating acrylic CFRTPs. It was observed that the copolymer matrices adhered well to the surfaces of CFs. The hydroxyethyl acrylamide (HEAA) copolymer having both amide groups and hydroxyl groups showed high adhesive strengths to CFs, which resulted in the high flexural strengths of the CFRTPs. The flexural strength of the CFRTPs having the HEAA co-polymerized acrylic matrices achieved the two-fold flexural strength (900 MPa), compared to the pure PMMA CFRTPs. This strength was equivalent level to the epoxy CFRP. Also, the increased interfacial adhesion led to delay of the delamination of the laminates, which gave the difference in the fracture mode and the improvement in fatigue resistance.

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